

Survey: How do people who do not have stable housing use digital media?

This survey is being conducted by Berlin University of the Arts. It is intended to help us understand how people who are not stably housed use digital media (smartphones, Internet, ...).

The results will be completely anonymised. This means we will be unable to connect the information you give to you personally. We will not be sharing your replies with charities or state authorities.

You are able to skip almost any question if you are not comfortable with them. We would appreciate if you try and complete as many of the questions as possible.

If you need help understanding the question, have any questions, or want to finish the survey, please let us know.

Thank you for agreeing to fill out this survey. It should take about 15-25 minutes. You will be receiving 10€ compensation after finishing the survey. You will receive this compensation regardless of how you answer the questions.

If you have any further needs, we are happy to try to connect you with a charity that will try to help.

* Indicates required question

Participation

1. Where are you filling out this questionnaire? (the interviewer will help you answer this) *

2. Name of interviewer:

 Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

-
-
-
-
-

3. Do you want to participate in this survey? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. Have you participated in this survey before? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Device ownership

5. Check all of the devices you currently own.

Tick all that apply.

Smartphone

Phone without internet (Button cellphone, "Dumb Phone")

Charging bank

Radio

Laptop

Tablet

Headphones

Camera

Other: _____

Internet/Smartphone usage last year

6. Have you you used the internet or any kind of smartphone or digital device in the last year? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No *Skip to question 56*

Only a phone without internet *Skip to question 30*

Smartphone ownership

7. Do you currently own a smartphone? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 8*

No *Skip to question 13*

Smartphone ownership continued

8. How did you get your most recent smartphone?

Mark only one oval.

Bought new

Bought used

Gift from family or friends

Donation from NGO

Other: _____

9. Did you get your most recent smartphone while you were housed, or while you were homeless?

Mark only one oval.

While I was housed

While I was homeless

Don't know

10. How much (approximately) did you spend on your most recent smartphone?

Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- Did not spend anything
- Less than 20 Euro
- 20-50 Euro
- 50-70 Euro
- 70-100 Euro
- 100-150 Euro
- 150-250 Euro
- 250-500 Euro
- More than 500 Euro
- Don't know

11. How well does your most recent smartphone work?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Rea Incredibly well - opens all the newest apps smoothly, takes great photots, ...

12. How many smartphones do you currently own?

Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- more than 4

Internet access points

13. How often have you used the internet in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Less: More than 4 hours a day

14. Have you used WiFi in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

15. If you used WiFi at any point in the last 12 months, where did you use it?

Check all options that apply. If you did not use WiFi, please skip question.

Tick all that apply.

Public transport (U-Bahn, Train stations, ...)

Cafés

Free Wifi Berlin (available throughout public places)

Shops (e.G. Lidl, Galeria)

Restaurants (McDonald's, ...)

Libraries

NGOs/charities

Friends and family

My own WiFi in a flat/room/...

Other: _____

16. How many GB (Gigabytes) of mobile data (3G/4G/5G) did you use per month on average in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1-3 GB
- 3-5 GB
- 5-10 GB
- 10-20 GB
- More than 20 GB
- I don't know

17. Have you used a laptop/computer in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

18. If you used a laptop/computer in the last 12 months, where?

Check all that apply. If you did not use a laptop/computer in the last 12 months, please skip this question.

Tick all that apply.

- Computer/laptop provided by NGO/charity
- Computer/laptop provided by library
- Computer/laptop in Internet Cafes
- Computer/laptop of friends or family
- My own computer/laptop
- Other: _____

App Usage

"Apps" are the programmes that run on smartphones.

19. Which of these messaging apps have you used in the last 12 months to message people?

Check all that apply. Messaging apps are apps you use to message other people.

Tick all that apply.

- WhatsApp
- Facebook Messenger
- Telegram
- Viber
- Email (Gmail, Outlook, iMail, ...)
- Texting / SMS
- Signal
- Other: _____

20. Which of these social media apps have you used in the last 12 months?

Check all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- Facebook
- Instagram
- TikTok
- VK
- Twitter
- Other: _____

21. Which of these other apps have you used in the last 12 months?

Check all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- YouTube
- Maps
- Browser (Chrome, Safari, ...)
- Music Streaming Apps: Spotify, Deezer, Apple Music, ...
- Video Streaming Apps: Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, Disney Plus, ...
- Dating Apps: Tinder, Grindr, Bumble, ...
- Apps specifically targeted to homeless people (Kältehilfe App, Mokli App, ...)
- Weather apps
- Telephone
- Other: _____

What do you use your phone/the internet for?

22. Did you go online or use your phone to do the following things in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
Look for information on the price of a product	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Look for jobs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Learn new things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Look for places to sleep, stay, eat, shower, ...	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What do you use your phone for? (continued)

23. Did you go online or use your phone to do the following things in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
Interact with people in online communities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arrange meeting up with people I know	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Talk to family or friends who live further away	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Comment about a political or societal issue	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Check the weather forecast	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What do you use your phone for? (continued)

24. Did you go online or use your phone to do the following things in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
Look for information about welfare services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Stay in contact with social workers / NGOs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Look up information about your health	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Look for financial information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meet new people (either online or in person)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What do you use your phone for? (continued)

25. Did you go online or use your phone to do the following things in the last 12 months?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
Consult others' opinions on problems or issues that interest you	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Play games	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Watch videos	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Find your way around the city	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Listen to music	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Usage outcomes

26. Which of the following apply to you?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
The information I found online improved my financial situation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The internet allows people to contact me who I don't want to be contacted by	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Through the internet, I've learned new things about homelessness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Through the internet, I've found people who share my interests	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Usage Outcomes

27. Which of the following apply to you?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
I am afraid of getting into debt on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have better relationships with my friends and family because I use the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have discovered online that I am entitled to a particular benefit that I would not have found offline	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The internet has made me trust people less	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Usage outcomes (continued)

28. Which of the following apply to you?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
I make better decisions about my health as a result of the information I found online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My knowledge has increased because of the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am worried I spend too much time on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online entertainment makes me feel happier in life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Ergebnisse der Internetnutzung

29. Which of the following apply to you?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes, a lot	Yes, a little	Neither true nor untrue	No, not very much	No, not at all
Using the internet makes me feel more lonely	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My phone allows me to tune out my surroundings and have some privacy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am more stressed out because of having a phone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am too dependent on the internet.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My phone gives me a sense of security.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Difficulties with phones

30. How difficult do you think getting a SIM card is in Germany?

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	
Very	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Very easy

31. Do you currently own a German SIM card that is registered to your name?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Don't know

32. Do you know how to buy SIM cards in Germany that are not registered to your name?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Don't know

33. Do you own a working SIM card that you bought in Germany that is not registered to your name?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Don't know

34. Do you currently own a working SIM card from another country?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

35. SIM card provider:

Tick all that apply.

- Ortel
- Lycamobile
- Ay Yildiz
- O2
- Vodafone
- Telekom
- Aldi Talk
- Other: _____

36. In the last 12 months, how much money do you spend on phone plans / phone credit each month?

 Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- Up to 5 Euros
- 5 - 10 Euros
- 10 - 20 Euros
- 20-30 Euros
- 30-50 Euros
- More than 50 Euros

37. Have you backed up some of your information (passwords, contacts, photos, ...) in the cloud or on a storage device?

Tick all that apply.

- Yes, in the cloud (Google, Apple, Microsoft, Dropbox, ...)
- Yes, on a storage device (usb drive, flash drive, micro-SD card, ...)
- No
- Don't know

38. How often do you change your phone number?

Mark only one oval.

- More than monthly
- Monthly
- Multiple times a year
- Around once every year
- Every few years
- Never

39. If you do change your phone number sometimes, why?

Check all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- Because of losing my phone, breaking it, or having it stolen
- To get a cheaper offer
- So people won't know my new number
- Because the SIM stopped working
- Other: _____

40. How difficult is it for you to charge electronic devices?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very difficult

41. Where/how did you charge your devices in the last 12 months? Tick all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- Bus
- NGOs/charities
- Friends' or family's flats
- Portable charger banks
- Train stations
- Cafes/Shops/Restaurants
- At work
- Tapped into a streetlight or similar
- Other: _____

42. How many times did you lose a smartphone, break it, or have it stolen in the last year (approximately)?

Mark only one oval.

- Never
- One time
- Twice
- Three times
- Four times
- Five times
- More than five times

43. Which of the following happen to you last year?

Check all that apply

Tick all that apply.

- My smartphone was stolen
- I broke my smartphone
- I lost my smartphone
- I had to sell my smartphone to make money
- Other: _____

Social network

44. Who did you spend time with face to face in the last 12 months?

Check all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- Friends/acquaintances who are housed
- Friends/acquaintances who are homeless
- Family members who are housed
- Family members who are unhoused
- Social workers
- New people / people I don't know
- Other: _____

45. Who did you communicate with by internet or phone, (by messaging, email, texting, ...) in the last 12 months?

Check all that apply

Tick all that apply.

- Friends/acquaintances who are housed
- Friends/acquaintances who are homeless
- Family members who are housed
- Family members who are homeless
- Social workers
- New people / people I don't know
- The place/organisation/... where I sleep
- Other: _____

Internet Skills

46. "I know how to open downloaded files"

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

47. "I know how to adjust privacy settings".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

48. "I find it hard to decide what the best keywords are to use for online searches".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

49. "I find it easy to find a website I visited before".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

50. "I know which information I should and shouldn't share online".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

51. "I know how to remove people from my contact lists".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

52. "I know how to make basic changes to the content that others have produced" (photo editing, changing texts, ...).

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

53. "I am confident about writing a comment on a blog, website or forum".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

54. " I know how to install apps on a mobile device".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

55. "I find it difficult to keep track of the costs of mobile app use".

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Somewhat true of me
- Very true of me
- Don't know

Internet Attitude

56. "I sometimes feel intimidated by the internet".

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

57. "The thought of going on the internet is fun to me".

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

58. "The use of the internet has enhanced people's standard of living".

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

59. "Using the internet is harmful to people"

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

About yourself

60. How old are you?

61. What gender do you identify with?

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

Other

Other: _____

62. How would you describe your sexual orientation?

Mark only one oval.

Heterosexual

Homosexual

Attracted to more than one gender (bisexual, panssexual, ...)

Prefer not to say

Other: _____

63. What languages do you speak?

Check all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- German
- English
- Russian
- Polish
- Lithuanian
- Romanian
- Bulgarian
- Chechen
- French
- Arabic
- Turkish
- Other: _____

64. How would you rate your knowledge of the German language?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3 4

_____ No k Perfectly fluent (or mother tongue)

65. What citizenship(s) do you have?

Tick all that apply.

- German
- EU (not Germany)
- Outside of EU

66. Are you usually perceived by other people to be a white, German person?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, always
- Sometimes
- No, never
- Don't know

67. What was the last institution the educational system that you visited?

Dropdown

Choose the one which best matches you.

Mark only one oval.

- Did not take part in formal education
- Primary school / Elementary School
- Secondary school / High School
- Vocational school / apprenticeship
- University

68. What are the ways in which you are getting money right now?

Check all that apply.

Tick all that apply.

- Job with a contract (full-time, part-time, 450 Euro)
- Odd jobs (working irregularly/without formal contracts)
- Collecting bottles
- Asking passersby for money
- Selling street papers
- Receiving money from family/friends
- State benefits (Hartz IV, Grundsicherung, Arbeitslosengeld I ...)
- Compensation for volunteer work
- Pension
- Other: _____

69. Do you have access to a bank account?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

70. How difficult is it for you to meet your basic needs (food, clothing, hygiene etc)

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very easy

Your housing situation

71. Which of these places did you sleep at in the last year? *

Tick all that apply.

- Night shelter (have to leave every morning)
- Residence for homeless people (can stay for longer period of time)
- Supported Housing (where a social worker supports you)
- Staying with friend or family member
- Living on the street, tent, in a park, or similar
- Living in a flatshare / flat without your own rental contract
- Living in a flatshare / flat with your own rental contract
- Occupied house
- Tiny House
- Hospital / Psychiatric Facility
- Jail
- Other: _____

72. Have you ever been homeless? *

"Homelessness" means not having access to some fixed, regular, and adequate nighttime residence.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

73. When was the last time you lived in your own room/apartment/other kind of permanent home? *

Choose the answer that best fits you - don't worry about being 100% correct.

Mark only one oval.

- Right now
- Less than 1 month ago
- 1-3 months ago
- 3-6 months ago
- 6-12 months ago
- 12 months - 5 years ago
- 5 years - 10 years
- Longer than 10 years ago
- I don't know

74. If you add together all the months/years in your life that you have been homeless, how long would you guess was this altogether? *

Choose the answer that best fits you - don't worry about being 100% correct.

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 month
- 1-3 months
- 3-6 months
- 6-12 months
- 12 months - 5 years
- 5 years - 10 years
- Longer than 10 years
- I don't know

75. How long have you been in Berlin for?

If you have been back and forth, add up all of your time in Berlin. Don't worry about being 100% accurate.

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 month
- 1-3 months
- 3-6 months
- 6-12 months
- 12 months - 5 years
- 5 years - 10 years
- Longer than 10 years
- I don't know

Health

This information helps us to see trends in the population - we anonymise all results and will not be able to identify any of your personal information.

76. Over the last 12 months, how would you say your health has been?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very good

77. Over the last 12 months, how would you say your mental health has been?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very good

78. Do you consider yourself to have a physical or mental disability?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Prefer not to say

Drug and alcohol usage

79. How often have you had 6 or more alcoholic drinks, on a single occasion, in the last year?

Mark only one oval.

- Never
- Less than monthly
- Monthly
- Weekly
- Daily or almost daily
- Prefer not to say

80. How often in the past year have you used a recreational drug or used a prescription medication for non-medical reasons?

Mark only one oval.

- Never
- Less than monthly
- Monthly
- Weekly
- Daily or almost daily
- Prefer not to say

Pandemic and Smartphone

81. Have you used a smartphone or the internet since the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic?

*

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 82*

No *Skip to question 87*

Covid-19 (internet-related questions)

82. How has your spending on being digitally connected (your phone, data plans, ...) changed since the pandemic?

Mark only one oval.

I've spent more

I've spent less

I'm spending roughly the same

I don't know

83. Has the Covid-19 pandemic made it more difficult to charge your devices?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

I don't know

84. How has your internet usage developed since the beginning of the pandemic?

Mark only one oval.

Decreased significantly

Somewhat decreased

Stayed the same

Somewhat increased

Increased significantly

Don't know

85. Do you access information about Covid-19 online?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

86. If you access information about Covid-19 online, where?

Check all that apply

Tick all that apply.

- News websites/news pages/...
- Social Media
- Messaging with friends or family
- German government websites (Berlin's web portal, Robert Koch Institute, ...)
- International government websites
- Websites of organisations working with homeless people
- Videos (YouTube, ...)
- Other: _____

Covid-19

87. Has the Covid-19 pandemic made it more difficult to organise your life?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, a lot
- Yes, somewhat
- Neither yes nor no
- No, not much
- No, not at all
- I don't know

88. Do you have a digital vaccine certificate?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, on a phone
- Yes, as a QR code
- Yes, on a phone and as a QR code
- No

89. If you have a digital vaccine certificate, do you know where you could get it again if you lost your phone?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't have a digital vaccine certificate

90. Have you ever been asked/forced to leave a place (like a train station) because you were unable to provide a (digital) vaccination certificate?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

91. Has the Covid-19 pandemic led to new opportunities for you (e.g. temporary housing, contact to new NGOs, improved or new services, more donations ...)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, a lot
- Yes, somewhat
- Neither yes nor no
- No, not much
- No, not at all
- I don't know

92. Do you always know about the latest Covid regulations?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

No, I Yes, I am always well informed

93. Have you been vaccinated against Covid-19?

You do not need to answer this question if you don't want to. Just check "prefer not to say".

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, once
- Yes, twice
- Yes, three times
- No *Skip to question 94*
- Prefer not to say *Skip to question 94*

Thanks for participating

If you have any last questions or comments, let us know. Afterwards, click on "send" and alert the person carrying out the questionnaire.

94. Do you have any questions or comments for us?

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